

Efficient heat recovery for temperature swing processes: Experimental analysis of the thermal wave method

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ABSTRACT

Industrial processes release large amounts of ultralow-grade heat, mostly unused due to inefficient recovery technologies. This study explores the thermal wave method as a heat recovery (HR) strategy for temperature swing adsorption (TSA) heat conversion (e.g. adsorption cooling) and gas separation (e.g. direct air capture) processes, where the rejection of large fraction of the heat input to the environment limits their scalability. A dedicated experimental setup was developed to quantify recovery with robust performance metrics, addressing inconsistencies in prior studies. Experiments in the range of temperatures between 30 °C and 80 °C achieved 55 % of heat input recovered, further improved to 61.5 % with a regenerative heat exchanger, surpassing conventional TSA thermal management strategies. Efficiency proved highly sensitive to flowrates, with an optimum in the range between 0.12 and 0.15 L min⁻¹ of the internal energy recovery loop. A predictive model, parameterised using the number of transfer units and effective heat capacity, captured dynamic behaviour with ~3.3 % variance. This work provides the first systematic validation of the thermal wave method, demonstrating >60 % efficiency and establishing a pathway to more commercially viable TSA and related thermal systems.

1. Introduction

Low-grade heat emissions at temperatures between ambient and 150 °C have been estimated at 2437 TWh yr⁻¹ in the EU (including the UK) [1] and 9316 TWh yr⁻¹ in the US [2]. These values primarily reflect conventional power generation, a sector undergoing rapid change, and exclude emerging contributors such as data centres and renewable energy transformers [3]. Within this spectrum, ultralow-grade heat (ambient to 80 °C) represents a particularly large but underutilised resource [4]. Harnessing this fraction is critical to a future zero-carbon energy system, yet economically viable technologies to exploit it remain scarce and rarely reach high technology readiness levels. Several ultralow-grade heat-powered processes have been demonstrated, including desalination [5], dehumidification [6], water harvesting [7], trace gas removal [8]. Recent studies have further broadened the strategies available for ultralow-grade heat use, demonstrating the advantage they bring to solar thermal systems [9–11].

In many cases, temperature swing adsorption (TSA) emerges as a valid technology to enable the exploitation of ultralow-grade heat. Recent advances in materials science have lowered the minimum temperature required to regenerate TSA adsorbents [12,13], extending

applicability into the ultralow-grade range. However, TSA processes remain energy-intensive, since a large share of the input heat is wasted as sensible heating and cooling of auxiliary components [14]. Without efficient heat recovery (HR), the adsorption capacity per unit of energy input remains too low for commercialisation due to the continuous waste from swinging the temperatures [15]. Furthermore, for heat inputs below 80 °C, recovery becomes less technically feasible due to the limited temperature gradients available for heat transfer and the inherently low second-law efficiency [16].

To address this, a variety of HR methods have been explored, with the most straightforward and commonly used HR technique involving circulating a heat transfer fluid (*htf*) between two beds following adsorption and desorption steps [17]. Conventional approaches, such as recuperative counterflow heat exchangers or direct bed-to-bed coupling, achieve only modest savings (10–25 % of energy input) [18,19] and show declining performance below 80 °C due to reduced driving temperature gradients [20]. Advanced concepts, including regenerative cycles and thermal storage, have been proposed to overcome these thermodynamic limitations [21–24].

Table 1 summarises representative HR studies in the ultralow-grade range, highlighting both their promise and the heterogeneity of performance indicators used to report efficiency. The efficiency of HR

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Nomenclature		htf	heat transfer fluid in the internal loop
A	heat transfer area [m ²]	m	mass [kg]
C	heat capacity rate [W K ⁻¹]	\dot{m}	mass flowrate [kg min ⁻¹]
(mC_p) _{eff}	effective heat capacity [W K ⁻¹]	NTU	number of transfer units [dimensionless]
COP	coefficient of performance [dimensionless]	OPT	optimised piping and insulation on the test rig
c_p	specific heat [kJ kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	q_{in}	thermal power input [W]
Cr	heat capacity ratio [dimensionless]	Q_{in}	total amount of thermal energy [J]
CU	cold utility heat exchanger	t	time [sec]
DC	direct cooling method	TH	high temperature setpoint
DH	direct heating method	TL	low temperature setpoint
DT	temperature difference performance indicator [dimensionless]	TSA	temperature swing adsorption
HR	heat recovery	T_{xx}	temperature at specified location xx [°C]
HU	hot utility heat exchanger	U	overall heat transfer coefficient [W m ⁻² K ⁻¹]
		ϵ	effectiveness [dimensionless]
		η_{TW}	thermal wave efficiency [dimensionless]

solutions is a metric defined differently across studies. Reconciling methods under common metrics is challenging, despite the general agreement on heat-input reduction between 17 % and 55 %. This heterogeneity underscores the need for unified performance metrics.

Among advanced concepts, the thermal wave method—which transfers heat dynamically between two thermal loads via a propagating

temperature front—has shown exceptional promise in theoretical analyses [27]. However, only a small number of experimental studies have validated the thermal wave method. For example, Qian reported an efficiency of ~60 % [25], but the study was limited to a narrow operating range, and the efficiency was based on an idealised model. More broadly, inconsistencies in the definition and reporting of efficiency (e.

Table 1
Comparison of reported HR methods/systems used on TSA processes with efficiencies.

Application	Adsorber Type	HR method	Temp. range	Cycle Time	Heat Transfer Type	Scale	Efficiency	Ref.
Air Dehumidification	Coated Heat Exchangers	Recuperative counterflow heat exchanger on the air-side	40 °C–60 °C	~40–60 min (per cycle)	Air (process & regeneration streams)	Lab-scale prototype	55 % reduction in heat input and a 16.3 % reduction in electrical power consumption.	[18]
Adsorption cooling	Coated Heat Exchangers	Pre-heating & Pre-cooling the TSA beds by opening the TSA beds to each other for mass and heat recovery	30 °C–80 °C	~600–1200 s (10–20 min)	Water (hot/cold water loop)	Lab-scale adsorption chiller	17–22 % reduction in heat input relative to operation without heat recovery.	[19]

Fig. 1. (a) Conceptual scheme of the thermal wave method, direction of the internal flow is both clockwise and anti-clockwise to reflect the two steps of Table 2; (b) Concept of the direct heating/cooling method. In both cases, the thermal load includes a stream for the heat transfer fluid and connections for the gas or vapour stream of adsorbate.

Table 2
Thermal Wave operation.

Steps	Heat Transfer Fluid Circulation	Adsorber A	Adsorber B
1	Anticlockwise	TL → TH Initial temperature of Bed A: TL Objective: Heating Bed A to the initial temperature of Bed B (TH)	TH → TL Initial temperature of Bed B: TH Objective: Cooling Bed B to the initial temperature of Bed A (TL)
2	Clockwise	TH → TL Initial temperature of Bed A: TH Objective: Cooling Bed A to the initial temperature of Bed B (TL)	TL → TH Initial temperature of Bed B: TL Objective: Heating Bed B to the initial temperature of Bed A (TH)

g., Miles' coefficient of performance (COP) vs Qian's efficiency metric [26] hamper cross-comparison. Four experimental evaluations exist in the literature, and none systematically benchmark performance against standardised metrics under TSA-relevant ultralow-grade conditions.

This knowledge gap motivates the present work. The experiments in this study achieve a record HR of 61.5 %, exceeding prior regenerative approaches. Equally significant is the introduction of a robust performance metric, which enables practical benchmarking of HR methods and supports technology comparison across studies. In addition, the development of a dynamic model, parameterised with only two experimentally regressed quantities (number of transfer units NTU and effective heat capacity), provides a predictive tool that can be directly applied in system design and scale-up. Together, these contributions extend the impact of the results beyond this specific setup, offering a practical framework to assess and optimise ultralow-grade HR in TSA processes. In summary, this work establishes the thermal wave method as the most effective HR strategy for TSA processes operating with ultralow-grade heat. By demonstrating efficient recovery under realistic conditions and introducing a generalised performance metric, it advances beyond previous studies and provides a pathway toward more energy-efficient separation technologies.

2. The thermal wave heat recovery method

Shelton et al. [27,28] [29] first introduced the principles of the thermal wave method for a solid/vapour adsorption heat transformer. The method recuperates high fractions of sensible heat between two identical thermal loads by creating a steep temperature step from a low temperature setpoint (TL) to a high temperature setpoint (TH). The temperature front travels all along the bed length during one half-cycle time and travels in the reverse direction during the other half-cycle time. Fig. 1 and Table 2 illustrate the principle of operation of the thermal wave method. While the direct heating/cooling [DH/DC] method is shown in (Fig. 1b), where DH is a temperature step experiment in which the thermal load temperature undergoes a step-change from TH to TL, and vice versa for DC. The thermal wave method holds the unique ability to maintain high recovery at low driving temperature differences (<80 °C), working at any given temperature range. Unlike steady-state recuperative designs that suffer diminishing gradients, the propagating temperature front inherent to thermal wave operation sustains effective heat transfer, minimising system irreversibility and improving recovery efficiency. Furthermore, thermal wave cycles can substantially improve system performance by recycling adsorption heat, thereby reducing external energy input requirements.

Several theoretical analyses have quantified the performance of the thermal wave method for design purposes in adsorption heating and cooling [26,30–34]. Simulation studies by Pons [25], reported that the COP could reach 1.18, demonstrating the strong potential of this approach. However, despite this theoretical advantage, the practical implementation of thermal wave cycles remains highly challenging, still

Table 3
Summary of key theoretical and experimental studies on thermal-wave and internally regenerated adsorption cycles, compared against the present work.

Ref.	System/Application	Method & Scale	Key Findings Relevant to Heat Recovery/COP	Relation to Present Work
[28]	Solid-vapour heat pump (ramp-wave model)	Theoretical analysis	Established ramp-wave behaviour in solid/vapour systems; no experiments.	Offers travelling-wave theory but no measurable heat-recovery data.
[30]	Convective thermal-wave adsorption cycle	Dynamic modelling (carbon-ammonia)	Bed-scale model showing COP sensitivity to heat-transfer effectiveness and cycle conditions.	Predictive only; lacks experimental thermal-wave recovery data.
[31]	Thermal-wave adsorption refrigeration (methanol)	Lab-scale experiments	Improved COP from 0.04 to 0.13, confirming feasibility at low temperatures.	First experimental thermal-wave test, but efficiency is modest, and the heat-recovery fraction is not reported.
[27]	Two-bed solid-sorption heat pump (NH ₃)	Lab-scale prototype	Internal heat recovery raised COP from ~1.21 to ~1.59.	Shows regenerative benefits but does not isolate thermal-wave recovery.
[26]	Solid-state cooling with HR cycle	Model + experiments	Achieved ~60 % heat-recovery efficiency in counter-flow HR (15–35 °C).	Gives a quantitative HR benchmark, though not adsorption-based.
[33]	Adsorption heat pump with internal regeneration	Theoretical + numerical	COP improvements predicted with high regeneration effectiveness.	Indicates potential gains but is not specific to travelling-wave dynamics.
[34]	Advanced adsorption cycles (incl. thermal-wave)	Thermodynamic evaluation	Compared architectures; COPs up to ~1.4 in multi-reactor heating cycles.	Cycle-level comparison: provides no direct heat recovery metrics.
This work	Thermal-wave heat recovery for TSA	Experiments + dynamic model	Demonstrated up to 61.5 % heat recovery using ultralow-grade heat; identified optimal flow-rate range; validated reproducibility; proposed 2-parameter predictive model.	First systematic experimental demonstration of >60 % thermal-wave heat recovery under TSA-relevant conditions, linking theory and practice.

Fig. 2. (a) Process flow diagram of thermal wave arrangement used in this study. Items needed for enhancing the heat recovery through heat regeneration are coloured in green and are optional. Thick lines indicate those used during heating of the thermal load α © M. Mohammed and G. Santori, The University of Edinburgh, 2025; (b) Representation of the spatial arrangement of the temperatures ($T_{\alpha,3}$, $T_{\alpha,4}$, T_{THC7} , T_{THC3} , T_{TH} , T_{TL}) through the loop during heating of load α ; (c) Temporal trend of the temperatures ($T_{\alpha,3}$, $T_{\alpha,4}$, T_{THC7} , T_{THC3} , T_{TH} , T_{TL}) emphasising the gradient between $T_{\alpha,3}$ and $T_{\alpha,4}$ even at half-cycle time and the different initial condition of the temperatures $T_{\alpha,3}$, $T_{\alpha,4}$ when the thermal front is not perfectly sharp and the cycle-time cannot be practically extended further for the two temperatures to match.

largely confined to the conceptual stage and lacks sufficient experimental confirmation. Miles et al. conducted lab-scale experiments to validate the principle of operation in a sorption heat pump, mostly focusing on the coupled effect of the thermal and fluid dynamics on the propagation of the temperature, measuring an increase in the COP from 1.21 to 1.59 [26]. Qian [25] compared three lab-scale experimental tests with an idealised dynamic model, reaching 60 % efficiency (defined as measured recovered heat input to an ideal model heat input) in an operational temperature range between 15 and 35 °C. Despite record recovery, only a small body of experimental research can confirm the practical viability of the thermal wave HR method, and the solutions proposed achieved HR significantly lower than expected [22]. Furthermore, the studies used heterogeneous metrics to quantify the HR efficiency as shown in Table 3.

This is a barrier to the systematic understanding of the limits and advantages of the method. This study aims to

- Experimentally validate the thermal wave heat recovery performance for TSA-relevant ultralow-grade heat conditions, addressing the scarcity of empirical data.
- Employ standardised performance metrics to resolve inconsistencies in prior reporting, including the HR efficiency or recovered energy, and a temperature difference approach metric (DT) grounded in pinch-analysis principles.
- Explore the influence of operational parameters (e.g., internal flow rate) on system performance and dynamics, providing design directions.
- Demonstrate the feasibility for ultralow-grade applications.
- Support industrial decarbonisation by enabling recovery of ultralow-grade waste heat that would otherwise remain unused.

3. Experimental setup

Fig. 2 shows the practical flow diagram of the concept in Fig. 1. Specifications of the equipment used in the corresponding test rig are reported in Table S1. The rig consists of two commercial gasketed stainless steel plate heat exchangers (thermal load α and β) used to emulate the adsorbers, replicating their temperature transient during alternation of cooling and heating steps. This approach makes the results generalisable to multiple TSA designs because it isolates the underlying linear dynamics of the thermal-wave, without overshadowing it with

Table 4

Operational Sequence of valves and the consequent state of the thermal loads during a cycle.

Step	Valves Closed	Valves Opened	Load α	Load β
1	SV2, SV4, SV6, SV9	SV1, SV3, SV5, SV10	Heating	Cooling
2	SV1, SV3, SV5, SV10	SV2, SV4, SV6, SV9	Cooling	Heating

Note: The addition of a regenerative heat exchanger (HEXR) to the standard cycle also needs additional valves, as reported in the scheme of Fig. 2 in green.

nonlinear effects associated with adsorption and desorption. In addition to the thermal loads, the system incorporates valves and pumps responsible for circulating the heat-transfer fluid (deionised water). Type K thermocouples (150 mm probes, accuracy ± 2.2 °C or ± 0.75 % of measured temperature) were calibrated in a thermostatic bath (Julabo F25). Nixon variable area flowmeters (accuracy class 2.5/4 VDI/VDE) relied on the manufacturer's calibration without further laboratory checks. Heat is supplied and removed via two brazed plate stainless steel heat exchangers, the hot utility heat exchanger HU and the cold utility heat exchanger CU, connected to two thermostatic baths. One single pump was used to reverse the internal loop *htf* flow, and a set of solenoid valves in an arrangement that maintains counter-current flow across all heat exchangers throughout the cycle. A reservoir tank stabilises the closed-loop flow during valve switching. Following the notation in Fig. 2a, T_{THC7} and T_{THC8} indicate the temperatures of the *htf* at the outlet and inlet of the hot utility HU, respectively, with the heat source providing heat at temperature T_{TH} . The *htf* flows through the two ends of the thermal load α in positions ($\alpha,3$) and ($\alpha,4$), while the other two ends are allocated to the adsorbate fluid. Similar notation applies to the thermal load β .

The thermal wave cycle operates in two alternating steps, controlled by the configuration of solenoid valves. In Step 1, valves SV2 and SV4 close together with SV6 and SV9, while valves SV1, SV3, SV5, and SV10 remain open. Under this arrangement, thermal load α heats up while thermal load β cools down. In Step 2, the flow reverses, with the following valve configuration: SV1, SV3, SV5, and SV10 closed, while SV2, SV4, SV6, and SV9 are opened. As a result, the thermal load α cools down, and the thermal load β heats up. Table 4 summarises this alternating sequence.

The operation of the thermal wave depends strongly on the internal loop *htf* flowrate and the flowrates of the external loops. Heating/

cooling switching intervals (half-cycle time) of 6 min were selected after preliminary trials. This duration was sufficient for the thermal front to traverse the plate-heat-exchanger loads under the tested operating conditions and reach operational steady state. This fixed half-cycle allowed to isolate only the effect of varying rates on the performance, in a range of internal loop *htf* flowrates from 0.04 L min⁻¹ to 0.4 L min⁻¹, while maintaining the external loops at 1.5 L min⁻¹ (heating) and 2.0 L min⁻¹ (cooling), with heating and cooling in the range from 30 °C up to 80 °C. Typical trends of the main temperatures, for example ($T_{\alpha,3}$, $T_{\alpha,4}$, T_{THC7} , T_{THC8} , T_{THC3} , T_{TH} , T_{TL}) for the case of load α heating from cold (Step 1 in Table 4) are as in Fig. 2b and c, through their location and throughout the whole duration of a half-cycle. A first reduction of the imposed temperature difference ($T_{TH} - T_{TL}$) occurs in HU and CU. This reduction becomes very small if the utility heat exchangers have a large surface area and operate with large utility flowrates. The average reduction across all tests in this study was ~ 1.1 °C, compared to the heat source and heat sink temperatures set in the thermal baths, as measured at the end of the half-cycle time. Therefore, for swinging the thermal load α from cold to hot, the temperature difference available ($\Delta T_{available}$) is:

$$\Delta T_{available} = \text{Max}(T_{THC7}) - \text{Min}(T_{THC3}) = T_{THC7}(t_{halfcycle,end}) - T_{THC3}(t_{halfcycle,end}) \quad (1)$$

Where $\text{Max}(T_{THC7})$ is the highest temperature measured in location THC7 and $\text{Min}(T_{THC3})$ is the lowest temperature measured in THC3, both occurring at the end of the half-cycle time.

If the cycle time is kept optimal in any operational condition, the flows are uniformly distributed, and the process is in all features perfectly symmetrical, the adsorbers can exploit the temperature difference available $\Delta T_{available}$ in full. In this case, since each end of the load stays connected to HU or to CU for the entire cycle, $T_{\alpha,4}$ is always hotter than $T_{\alpha,3}$ but both temperatures undergo the same temperature swing, shifted, as illustrated by Fig. 2b. These conditions are rarely met in practice, resulting in temperature gradients throughout the thermal load, during the entire operation. In practical conditions, some parts of load α could operate at the smallest temperature swing ΔT_{min} :

$$\Delta T_{min} = \text{Max}(T_{\alpha,3}) - \text{Min}(T_{\alpha,4}) = T_{\alpha,3}(t_{halfcycle,end}) - T_{\alpha,4}(t_{halfcycle,start}) \quad (2)$$

Where $\text{Max}(T_{\alpha,3})$ is the highest temperature measured in location ($\alpha,3$) at the end of the half-cycle time, and $\text{Min}(T_{\alpha,4})$ is the lowest temperature measured in ($\alpha,4$) at the start of the half-cycle time.

4. Thermodynamic and dynamic performance indicators

4.1. Efficiency

This study evaluates the heat recovery efficiency by comparing the heat input in the thermal wave method against the heat input without any HR – direct heating (DH). This way of defining HR efficiency has two advantages: (i) it frees from the need for an idealised theoretical model and its assumptions, as was done by Qian [25], (ii) the normalisation of the heat input on the DH case allows comparison among different HR methods. The HR efficiency of the thermal wave method is:

$$\eta_{TW} = 1 - \left(\frac{\int_{t_0}^{t_{halfcycle,end}} q_{in,TW} dt}{\int_{t_0}^{t_{steady-state}} q_{in,DH} dt} \right) = 1 - \frac{Q_{in,TW}}{Q_{in,DH}} \quad (3)$$

Where $q_{in,TW}$ [W] is the thermal power input from HU when using thermal wave and $Q_{in,TW}$ [J] is its integration over half-cycle time, after the cyclic steady state is achieved; $q_{in,DH}$ [W] is the thermal power input in direct heating and $Q_{in,DH}$ [J] is its integration until steady state (experiments in the Support Material). The power input $q_{in,TW}$ is from the experimental temperature and flowrates. For the thermal load α , it is:

$$q_{in,TW} = (\dot{m}_{TH} c_p)_{HU} (T_{TH} - T_{THC6}) \quad (4)$$

Where T_{TH} and T_{THC6} are the temperatures at the inlet and outlet of HU, \dot{m}_{TH} is the external flowrate of the hot utility heat transfer fluid (1.5 L min⁻¹ in all the tests), c_p and water density are averaged between the inlet and outlet values.

4.2. Dynamic performance indicator

As a thermodynamic metric, the efficiency η_{TW} fails to capture the system's dynamics. The performance indicator DT can compensate for this shortcoming. DT is the ratio between the minimum temperature swing achieved in the thermal load and the maximum available, obtained from equations (1) and (2):

$$DT = \frac{\Delta T_{min}}{\Delta T_{available}} \quad (5)$$

DT is a measure of the sharpness of the thermal front through the loads. A step-waved thermal front that travels from one end of the load α to the opposite precisely matches the following conditions:

$$T_{\alpha,3}(t_{halfcycle,start}) = T_{\alpha,4}(t_{halfcycle,start}) \quad (6)$$

$$T_{\alpha,3}(t_{halfcycle,end}) = T_{\alpha,4}(t_{halfcycle,end}) \quad (7)$$

$$T_{\alpha,4}(t_{halfcycle,end}) = T_{THC7}(t_{halfcycle,end}) \quad (8)$$

$$T_{\alpha,3}(t_{halfcycle,start}) = T_{THC3}(t_{halfcycle,end}) \quad (9)$$

In such a case, $DT = 1$. Imperfect cases that for any engineering reason (e.g., hydrodynamics) depart from the perfect case will produce $0 < DT < 1$.

5. Identification of the dynamics of the thermal loads

Fitting all energy balances describing the process over the experimental temperatures allows the retrieval of the characteristic heat transfer parameters, such as the number of transfer units (NTU) and the effective heat capacity of the thermal loads. When these are used in a validated mathematical model, the performance of the thermal wave method can be assessed across multiple operating conditions, without the need for additional tests. The model is made of two parts: the energy balance of the utility heat exchangers and the energy balance of the thermal loads.

The *Utility heat exchangers* HU and CU in Fig. 2a are counter-current stainless steel plate heat exchangers (see equipment specifications in Table S1 of the Support Material). They can be represented with a steady state effectiveness approach (ϵ -NTU) under two main assumptions.

- Steady-state operation. The accumulation of heat in the heat exchangers from changes in the inlet and outlet temperatures is negligible when the operational temperatures are close (see confirmation in Fig. S3 in the Support Material).
- Heat losses are negligible since HU and CU are insulated.

After defining the heat capacity rate of the utility heating/cooling streams $C_{max} = (\dot{m}c_p)_{utility}$ [W K⁻¹] and of the internal loop fluid $C_{min} = (\dot{m}c_p)_{htf}$ [W K⁻¹], along with the number of transfer units $NTU = UA/C_{min}$ [K s⁻¹] of each utility heat exchanger, their effectiveness is calculated from:

$$\epsilon = \frac{1 - \exp[-NTU(1 - C_r)]}{1 - C_r \exp[-NTU(1 - C_r)]} \quad (10)$$

, where $C_r = C_{min}/C_{max}$ and the NTU were retrieved from the steady-state

Table 5
Key input parameters used in the analysis.

Quantity	Symbol	Description	Units	Value
Heat sink set temperature	TL	Temperature of the heat sink	°C	30
Heat source set temperature	TH	Temperature of heat source	°C	50–80
Internal loop flow rate (<i>hif</i>)	–	Flow rate in the internal loop	L min ⁻¹	0.04–0.4
External hot-loop flow rate	–	Flow rate of the hot utility loop (HU)	L min ⁻¹	1.5
External cold-loop flow rate	–	Flow rate of cold utility loop (CU)	L min ⁻¹	2.0
Effective heat capacity of each thermal load	$mc_{p,eff}$	Lumped effective heat capacity of a thermal load	J K ⁻¹	282 (as regressed)
Number of transfer units of the thermal load	NTU	Dimensionless heat-transfer parameter of thermal loads	–	12.3 (as regressed)

experimental measurements, as detailed in the support material Fig. S2. The steady-state assumption is not viable for the thermal loads, where their NTU and effective heat capacity (mc_p)_{eff} affect the thermal response. These two parameters can be regressed from temperature-step experiments through an energy balance lumped parameters model [35] under two main assumptions:

- The overall dynamics of the load follow the dynamics of its volumetric average temperature T_α or T_β
- Heat losses are negligible since both load α and load β are insulated

For the thermal load α , the lumped parameters model during the heating step consists of the following set of two equations:

$$(\dot{m}c_p)_{hif} (T_{\alpha,3} - T_{\alpha,4}) = (mc_p)_{eff} dT_\alpha/dt \quad (11)$$

$$T_{\alpha,3} = T_{\alpha,4} + (T_{\alpha,3} - T_{\alpha,ini}) \exp[NTU t] \quad (12)$$

With the following initial condition

$$T_{\alpha,ini} = T_{\alpha,4} \text{ at } t = 0 \quad (13)$$

The same set of equations can be applied to the load β and in cooling mode, with different indices. The equations are not repeated here for the sake of brevity. The system of equations (11)–(13) was solved in

MATLAB ode45, applying a non-linear least-squares regression approach to fit the normalised temperature step data for the thermal loads (Support Material Fig. S5). After regression, the NTU and effective heat capacity (mc_p)_{eff} parameters of the thermal loads can be used for the prediction of the performance (η_{TW} , DT) in conditions where no experiments have been performed and for optimisation. The regression returned $NTU = 12.3$ and $(mc_p)_{eff} = 282 \text{ J K}^{-1}$, applicable to both the loads, given they are identical. Table 5 lists the input parameters used in this analysis using the developed model. Fig. 3 shows a thermal wave cycle, swinging from 30 °C to 60 °C. Model predictions are in agreement with experiments, validating the applicability of the approach and of the parameters.

The interval intercurrent between the two intersection points $T_{\alpha,3} \times T_{\beta,5}$, and $T_{\alpha,4} \times T_{\beta,6}$ is a straightforward way to qualitatively appreciate the sharpness of the thermal front, which is affected by the effective heat capacity and NTU of the thermal loads [25]. Short intervals reflect step-like waves.

The efficiency achieved (η_{TW}) in the experiment of Fig. 3 is 47.4 %,

Fig. 4. Comparison between experimental and model efficiency η_{TW} under different temperature swings (cold bath set-point = 30 °C; hot bath set-points = {50 °C; 60 °C; 70 °C; 80 °C}). Operating conditions: internal loop flow rate of 0.15 L min⁻¹, external loop flow rates of 1.5 L min⁻¹ (heating) and 2.0 L min⁻¹ (cooling).

Fig. 3. Temperature profiles of the thermal loads over one full cycle lasting 12 min: experimental measurements (solid-line) and model predictions (dashed-line) with $NTU = 12.3$ and $(mc_p)_{eff} = 282 \text{ J K}^{-1}$. Operating conditions: cold thermostatic bath set temperature is 30 °C, hot thermostatic bath set temperature is 60 °C, internal loop flow rate is 0.12 L min⁻¹, external loop flow rates are 1.5 L min⁻¹ (heating) and 2.0 L min⁻¹ (cooling). For this test, the experimental Heat Recovered (measured) = 47.4 % vs. the modelled Heat Recovered (model) = 45.7 %. The grey shaded area corresponds to the heat loading step, when heat has to be introduced in the device for the first time. The two halves of the cycle exhibit identical dynamics after reversal of the flow direction, confirming the successful application of the valves SV7 to SV10 to keep the flow in counter-current mode. The red-shaded and green-shaded areas are proportional to the heat input from the hot utility and the fraction of heat recovered.

Fig. 5. (a) On the left, the efficiency η_{TW} map (b) on the right, the DT map of the thermal wave heat-recovery method under variable internal flow rates (0.04–0.4 L min^{-1}) across a range of temperature swings (30 °C → 50–80 °C). The external loop flowrates for these tests were 1.5 L min^{-1} for heating and 2.0 L min^{-1} for cooling. OPT denotes tests performed after upgrading the piping to prevent pump water hammering and to improve degassing. HEXR denotes tests using the full installation including one regenerative heat exchanger and its auxiliary valves as in Fig. 2a (green). The shaded area indicates far from optimal operating regions where a fraction of the heat input bypasses thermal loads and is dumped into the cold utility.

with 45.7 % predicted by the model. The small discrepancy is mostly due to the steady state assumption of the utility heat exchangers (see analysis in Support Material). Replication of the comparison on a range of input temperatures (Fig. 4) shows the model keeps its validity, with a variance of 3.3 % between measured and modelled η_{TW} .

6. Thermal wave heat recovery and regenerative heat exchanger

6.1. Experimental analysis on thermal wave heat recovery

A systematic variation of the internal loop flowrate reveals the rate-controlled nature of the process. Fig. 5a–b maps η_{TW} and DT across varying temperature swings (cold bath set temperature = 30 °C → hot bath set temperature = 50–80 °C). Experiments denoted with OPT have been performed after upgrading the piping to prevent pump water hammering and to improve degassing. These modifications reduced experimental noise and improved the performance indicators and their reproducibility. The results show a clear optimum around 0.12–0.15 L min^{-1} , with a maximum efficiency of 55 % and $DT > 50$ %, ensuring both energy recovery and functional performance. While some tests at low internal loop flowrates of < 0.1 L min^{-1} reported $\eta_{TW} > 60$ %, they coincided with DT values < 50 % indicating that the thermal loads did not fully reach temperatures close enough to the hot source temperature. Such conditions are not invalid in practice, but they are sub-optimal from a system perspective: the process saves energy but fails to deliver the desired temperature level; thus, the temperature of the thermal loads remains too low. The result underscores that η_{TW} alone is not a sufficient metric of performance, and the ability to meet the required temperature, must be considered to avoid misleadingly optimistic efficiency values. This indicates that a trade-off exists between high efficiency and full exploitation of the temperature swing available (high DT). High flowrates of the internal loop (0.3–0.4 L min^{-1}) can result in sub-optimal and even negative efficiencies. The negative values of η_{TW} occur at excessively high internal flow rates, where the residence time within the

thermal loads becomes too short for effective heat transfer. Under these conditions, the hot fluid from the HU flows through the loads with minimal temperature change, rejecting the heat to the CU. The net energy penalty relative to DH, leads to negative η_{TW} .

This finding demonstrates how improper flowrate control can make the system counterproductive, emphasising the need to operate within the narrow range of optimal flowrates. The thermal wave method is highly sensitive to flowrate control, but under control of the optimal operational flowrate, can consistently achieve η_{TW} values > 50 % with $DT > 50$ %.

6.2. Optimisation of heat recovery using regenerative exchangers

Regenerative heat exchangers can further increase the recovery [21]. One extra heat exchanger (HEXR) can be added to the internal loop to preheat the cold thermal load and precool the hot thermal load, as highlighted in Fig. 2a (in green). The effect of the addition of HEXR is an increase in both the DT s and the η_{TW} . However, the added heat exchanger HEXR can be used only for a limited fraction of the cycle time to avoid deterioration of the efficiency. Evidence shows that using the HEXR for a full cycle interferes with the heating/cooling fronts, when the inlet and outlet temperatures of the two thermal loads invert.

When operated in defined intervals of time, the addition of the regenerative heat exchanger showed an increase in the efficiency η_{TW} up to 61.5 % (Fig. 5a and Table 6).

The portion of the cycle during which the HEXR provides an advantage was determined experimentally by monitoring the temperature fronts of the *htf* in each thermal load and identifying the interval where regeneration remains favourable. This favourable interval corresponds to the initial heating/cooling period (highlighted in Fig. S6), where the temperature of the *htf* leaving the thermal load being cooled (β in the example of Fig. 2) is higher than the temperature of the incoming stream to the thermal load being heated (α in the example of Fig. 2):

$$T_{\beta,6} > T_{\alpha,3} \tag{14}$$

Once the temperature fronts invert, continued use of the HEXR would introduce penalties. Thus, successful exploitation of the regenerative heat exchanger requires accurate monitoring and timing so that it operates only when it brings advantages.

Table 6

Efficiency η_{TW} (heat recovered) in the thermal wave process with one regenerative heat exchanger.

Cold set temperature/Hot set temperature	Efficiency η_{TW}
30 °C–50 °C	55.1 % ± 0.087
30 °C–60 °C	58.6 % ± 0.042
30 °C–70 °C	61.5 % ± 0.032

Note: Internal loop flowrate = 0.12 L min^{-1}

7. Conclusions

Experiments on a thermal wave heat recovery process showed that up to 61.5 % of the heat input can be recovered in temperature swing processes. This represents a meaningful advance in ultralow-grade heat utilisation, and the practical implications are substantial. Breaking the 60 % barrier in efficiency in ultralow-grade heat recovery drastically reduces the energy intensity of temperature swing adsorption cycles, lowering their operating cost and improving their viability in a multitude of applications such as cooling, carbon capture, water harvesting, and desalination. Importantly, these gains are achieved with modest infrastructure requirements, relying mainly on flow optimisation and limited hardware additions.

Due to the highly dynamic nature of the thermal wave, the heat recovered (η_{TW}) is governed by several interacting parameters. In particular, the internal loop flowrate strongly influences the balance between heat input and heat output, with an optimum identified at 0.12–0.15 L min⁻¹ (external loops: 1.5 L min⁻¹ heating, 2.0 L min⁻¹ cooling). Operation at this point ensured maximum heat recovery and demonstrated clear tunability of the process. Experiments showed key takeaways such as the importance of optimising flow-rates for maximising the fraction of heat recovered at the highest temperature, and the risk of incurring in energy penalties instead of recovery in certain conditions. A predictive dynamic model was developed to generalise the findings to other designs and operating conditions. The model requires only two experimentally regressed parameters, the number of transfer units of the adsorber NTU and the effective heat capacity of the adsorber, which can be determined from temperature step tests. This framework provides a practical design tool for system optimisation. Nevertheless, the state assumption applied to the utility heat exchangers constrain the model to all cases where the flow rate of the heating and cooling utility fluids is such that their temperature does not change significantly upon heat exchange with the internal loop fluid.

A measurable dynamic indicator (DT) informs on the thermal fronts and irreversible losses in the thermal wave method. Operation at high DT leads to sharp thermal fronts and reduces irreversibility losses — raising the temperature of the heat delivered to the thermal loads. DT thus complements η_{TW} for both design and operation, and a trade-off between high η_{TW} and high DT was observed for optimal operating conditions. Importantly, the experiments revealed conditions leading to negative efficiencies, where part of the heat input was rejected directly to the sink. The result emphasises the need for careful control of the method flowrates and highlights potential pitfalls for practical deployment.

The implementation of a single, strategically operated, regenerative heat exchanger increases the maximum recoverable heat by 6.5 % absolute, achieving a record efficiency of 61.5 %. This demonstrates the core innovative contribution of this study: that thermal-wave-enabled recovery can substantially exceed previously reported methods. Future work should explore the scalability of the concept and the influence of variable cycle times for practical application to temperature swing processes for separation (e.g., Direct Air Capture) or energy conversion (e.g., Adsorption Cooling, Adsorption Desalination), comprising of at least two adsorbers, where reducing regeneration energy demand is critical for economic viability. Ultimately, these results underline the broader implication that ultralow-grade heat — traditionally considered difficult to exploit — can be transformed into a valuable resource through thoughtfully engineered thermal-wave heat recovery.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Marwan Mohammed: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Giulio Santori:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition,

Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2025.139880>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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